

The Impact of Fuzzy Uncertainty On The Diabetic And Non Diabetic Covid Model

Vijayalakshmi G.M¹, Vikram²

¹Department of Mathematics,
Vel Tech Rangarajan Dr. Sagunthala R & D Institute of Science and Technology, Avadi,
Tamil Nadu, India – 600062.

²Department of Mathematics, DRBCCC Hindu College, Pattabiram, Tamil Nadu, India – 600072.

Abstract

In this work, we have discussed about SIR model with model using Michaelis – Menten Functional response and explained the deviations in the infections and the recovery from COVID-19 for the non-diabetic and diabetic patients. We also discussed about the uncertainty rate of change variables, so by using the concept of Fuzzy I have reduced the uncertainty and found a better model using Trapezoidal Fuzzy Numbers (TFN) and Basic Defuzzification Method (BDM). Also I have discussed about the equilibrium points and stability of the model and compared the variation between the crisp model and the Fuzzy model by using Matlab Software.

Keywords:

SIR model –TFN - BDM – Stability – Diabetics.

Introduction

As of June 2022 about 4.35 Crore people in India have been infected with the COVID-19 disease. But diabetes patients are more probably to have serious impediment from COVID-19. Generally, diabetes patients are more likely to have more rigorous symptoms and impediments when infected with any virus. They have high threat of getting very sick from COVID-19 and it is likely to be lower if the diabetes is well-handled.

In this work, we have discussed about SIR model with model using Michaelis – Menten Functional response and explained the deviations in the infections and the recovery from COVID-19 for the non-diabetic and diabetic patients. We also discussed about the uncertainty rate of change variables, so by using the concept of Fuzzy we have reduced the uncertainty and found a better model. Also we have discussed about the equilibrium points and stability of the model and compared the variation between the crisp model and the Fuzzy model.

Most of the researches has been done regarding the influence of COVID-19 virus within the patients affected with some other disease. Abdelfatah Kouidere et al [1] discussed about the negative impact of quarantine with the diabetics people. In his paper discusses about the disturbances in the regular practices in following diet control to overcome diabetics. Alok Aggarwal et al [2] in their work discusses that diabetics is to be vulnerable to the COVID-19 infected patients, their changes in the blood sugar level makes more complications to be recovered from the infection.

Ashish Kumar A et al [3] discussed the Fuzzy logic tool helps as computational prototype which gave them a mathematical tool for human reasoning for handling the various type uncertainties. He explained the way of finding solution for uncertainty using capability of fuzzy logic express the human knowledge in linguistic way. By considering these two cases, in this paper we have developed model considering the increase in the immune system in the human beings as the important parameter in the recovery from the infection. Also using the fuzzy inference system, I have shown the changes that can be rectified in the rate of changing parameters.

Preliminary Definitions

SIR Model

SIR stands for Susceptible – Infectious - Recovered, in this mathematical model there will be susceptible prey will be Infectious Prey and then it will be recovered. In this model I have discussed about two types of susceptible prey in which one has more possibilities of getting infected and less possibility of getting recovered.

Diabetes

A disease in which the body's ability to produce or respond to the hormone insulin is impaired, resulting in abnormal metabolism of carbohydrates and elevated levels of glucose in blood.

Fuzzification:

Fuzzification is the process of converting crisp environment into fuzzy environment whenever uncertainty occurs, by given the membership value for each and every element.

Trapezoidal fuzzy numbers (TFN):

The Trapezoidal fuzzy number is a fuzzy number represented with the point as $T = (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4)$. The fuzzy membership function is given by

$$\mu_{\underline{A}}(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & x < a_1 \\ \frac{x - a_1}{a_2 - a_1}, & a_1 \leq x \leq a_2 \\ 1, & a_2 \leq x \leq a_3 \\ \frac{a_4 - x}{a_4 - a_3}, & a_3 \leq x \leq a_4 \\ 0, & x > a_4 \end{cases}$$

Properties of Trapezoidal fuzzy numbers

- (i) a, b, c, d are natural numbers and satisfy Pythagorean quadruple identity, $a^2 = b^2 + c^2 + d^2$.
- (ii) if the GCD of a, b, c is 1, then the quadruple is called primitive.
- (iii) if (a, b, c, d) are Pythagorean quadruple, then (ka, kb, kc, kd) is also a quadruple for any positive whole number k .
- (iv) The Pythagorean quadruple can be generated from any two numbers m and n simply by setting $a = m^2, b = 2mn, c = n^2, d = (m + n)^2$

Defuzzification:

Defuzzification is the process of producing result in crisp logic for given fuzzy logic and membership degrees. It is a process of mapping crisp set from a fuzzy set.

Defuzzification for trapezoidal fuzzy number

Consider a fuzzy number (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) . We defuzzify this trapezoidal fuzzy number by partitioning the interval (a_1, a_4) as shown below:

$$(a_1, a_4) = A_1 \cup A_2 \cup A_3$$

Where $A_1 = (a_1, a_2), A_2 = (a_2, a_3)$ and $A_3 = (a_3, a_4)$. we define the triangular fuzzy numbers corresponding to A_1 and A_3 as $\tilde{l}_1 = (a_1, a_2, a_2)$ and $\tilde{l}_3 = (a_3, a_3, a_4)$ and obtain their corresponding real numbers denoted by l_1 and l_3 as follows:

$$l_1 = \frac{a_1 + a_2 + a_2}{3} = \frac{a_1 + 2a_2}{3}$$

$$l_3 = \frac{a_3 + a_3 + a_4}{3} = \frac{2a_3 + a_4}{3}$$

We obtain the real number l_2 corresponding to the interval $A_2 = (a_2, a_3)$, by using the mean relation as follows,

$$l_2 = \frac{a_2 + a_3}{2}$$

Now the mean of the numbers l_1, l_2, l_3 is considered as the crisp real number corresponding trapezoidal fuzzy number. The crisp real a is obtained by using the mean relation as follows:

$$a = \frac{l_1 + l_2 + l_3}{3}$$

$$a = \frac{2a_1 + 7a_2 + 7a_3 + 2a_4}{18}$$

NOTATION

X_1 – Non Diabetic Susceptible	r_1 – Non Diabetic infected rate
X_2 – Diabetic Susceptible	r_2 – Diabetic infected rate
X_3 – Non Diabetic Susceptible Infected	β_1 – Non Diabetic immune rate
X_4 – Diabetic Susceptible Infected	β_2 – Diabetic immune rate
X_5 – Recovered	δ_1 – Non Diabetic recovery rate from infection
α_1 – Birth rate	δ_2 – Diabetic recovery rate from infection
α_2 – Diabetic increasing rate	μ_1 – Normal death rate
	μ_2 – Infected death rate

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{dX_1}{dt} &= \alpha_1 X_1 - \frac{(\alpha_2 X_2 + r_1 X_3) X_1}{\beta_1} - \mu_1 X_1 \\ \frac{dX_2}{dt} &= \frac{\alpha_2 X_1 X_2}{\beta_1} - \frac{r_2 X_2 X_4}{\beta_2} - \mu_1 X_2 \\ \frac{dX_3}{dt} &= \frac{r_1 X_1 X_3}{\beta_1} - \delta_1 \beta_1 X_3 X_5 - \mu_2 X_3 \\ \frac{dX_4}{dt} &= \frac{r_2 (X_2 + X_5) X_4}{\beta_2} - \delta_2 \beta_2 X_4 X_5 - \mu_2 X_4 \\ \frac{dX_5}{dt} &= \delta_1 \beta_1 X_3 X_5 + \delta_2 \beta_2 X_4 X_5 - \frac{r_2 X_4 X_5}{\beta_2} - \mu_2 X_5 \end{aligned} \right\} \text{---(1)}$$

Diagrammatic representation of the Model

Figure. 1 Diagrammatic Representation of the Model

CASE - 2: FUZZY MODEL

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{d\tilde{X}_1}{dt} &= \alpha_1 X_1 \ominus \frac{(\tilde{\alpha}_2 X_2 \oplus \tilde{r}_1 X_3) X_1}{\tilde{\beta}_1} - \mu_1 X_1 \\ \frac{d\tilde{X}_2}{dt} &= \frac{\tilde{\alpha}_2 X_1 X_2}{\tilde{\beta}_1} \ominus \frac{\tilde{r}_2 X_2 X_4}{\tilde{\beta}_2} - \mu_1 X_2 \\ \frac{d\tilde{X}_3}{dt} &= \frac{\tilde{r}_1 X_1 X_3}{\tilde{\beta}_1} \ominus \delta_1 \tilde{\beta}_1 X_3 X_5 \ominus \tilde{\mu}_2 X_3 \\ \frac{d\tilde{X}_4}{dt} &= \frac{\tilde{r}_2 (X_2 + X_5) X_4}{\tilde{\beta}_2} \ominus \tilde{\delta}_2 \tilde{\beta}_2 X_4 X_5 \ominus \tilde{\mu}_2 X_4 \\ \frac{d\tilde{X}_5}{dt} &= \tilde{\delta}_1 \tilde{\beta}_1 X_3 X_5 \oplus \tilde{\delta}_2 \tilde{\beta}_2 X_4 X_5 \ominus \frac{\tilde{r}_2 X_4 X_5}{\tilde{\beta}_2} \ominus \tilde{\mu}_2 X_5 \end{aligned} \right\} \text{---(2)}$$

Where,

- $\tilde{\alpha}_2 = (\tilde{\alpha}_2 - \Delta_1, \tilde{\alpha}_2 - \Delta_2, \tilde{\alpha}_2 + \Delta_2, \tilde{\alpha}_2 + \Delta_1), 0 < \Delta_1 < \alpha_2 \text{ and } \Delta_2 > 0$
- $\tilde{r}_1 = (\tilde{r}_1 - \Delta_3, \tilde{r}_1 - \Delta_4, \tilde{r}_1 + \Delta_4, \tilde{r}_1 + \Delta_3), 0 < \Delta_3 < \tilde{r}_1 \text{ and } \Delta_4 > 0$
- $\tilde{r}_2 = (\tilde{r}_2 - \Delta_5, \tilde{r}_2 - \Delta_6, \tilde{r}_2 + \Delta_6, \tilde{r}_2 + \Delta_5), 0 < \Delta_5 < \tilde{r}_2 \text{ and } \Delta_6 > 0$
- $\tilde{\beta}_1 = (\tilde{\beta}_1 - \Delta_7, \tilde{\beta}_1 - \Delta_8, \tilde{\beta}_1 + \Delta_8, \tilde{\beta}_1 + \Delta_7), 0 < \Delta_7 < \tilde{\beta}_1 \text{ and } \Delta_8 > 0$
- $\tilde{\beta}_2 = (\tilde{\beta}_2 - \Delta_9, \tilde{\beta}_2 - \Delta_{10}, \tilde{\beta}_2 + \Delta_{10}, \tilde{\beta}_2 + \Delta_9), 0 < \Delta_9 < \tilde{\beta}_2 \text{ and } \Delta_{10} > 0$
- $\tilde{\delta}_1 = (\tilde{\delta}_1 - \Delta_{11}, \tilde{\delta}_1 - \Delta_{12}, \tilde{\delta}_1 + \Delta_{12}, \tilde{\delta}_1 + \Delta_{11}), 0 < \Delta_{11} < \tilde{\delta}_1 \text{ and } \Delta_{12} > 0$
- $\tilde{\delta}_2 = (\tilde{\delta}_2 - \Delta_{13}, \tilde{\delta}_2 - \Delta_{14}, \tilde{\delta}_2 + \Delta_{14}, \tilde{\delta}_2 + \Delta_{13}), 0 < \Delta_{13} < \tilde{\delta}_2 \text{ and } \Delta_{14} > 0$
- $\tilde{\mu}_2 = (\tilde{\mu}_2 - \Delta_{15}, \tilde{\mu}_2 - \Delta_{16}, \tilde{\mu}_2 + \Delta_{16}, \tilde{\mu}_2 + \Delta_{15}), 0 < \Delta_{15} < \tilde{\mu}_2 \text{ and } \Delta_{16} > 0$

CASE – 3: DEFUZZIFIED MODEL

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
 \text{defuzz}\left(\frac{d\tilde{X}_1}{dt}\right) &= \alpha_1 X_1 - \frac{(\text{defuzz}(\tilde{\alpha}_2)X_2 - \text{defuzz}(\tilde{r}_1)X_3)X_1}{\text{defuzz}(\tilde{\beta}_1)} - \mu_1 X_1 \\
 \text{defuzz}\left(\frac{d\tilde{X}_2}{dt}\right) &= \frac{\text{defuzz}(\tilde{\alpha}_2)X_1 X_2}{\text{defuzz}(\tilde{\beta}_1)} - \frac{\text{defuzz}(\tilde{r}_2)X_2 X_4}{\text{defuzz}(\tilde{\beta}_2)} - \mu_1 X_2 \\
 \text{defuzz}\left(\frac{d\tilde{X}_3}{dt}\right) &= \frac{\text{defuzz}(\tilde{r}_1)X_1 X_3}{\text{defuzz}(\tilde{\beta}_1)} - \text{defuzz}(\tilde{\delta}_1)\text{defuzz}(\tilde{\beta}_1)X_3 X_5 - \text{defuzz}(\tilde{\mu}_2)X_3 \\
 \text{defuzz}\left(\frac{d\tilde{X}_4}{dt}\right) &= \frac{\text{defuzz}(\tilde{r}_2)(X_2 + X_5)X_4}{\text{defuzz}(\tilde{\beta}_2)} - \text{defuzz}(\tilde{\delta}_2)\text{defuzz}(\tilde{\beta}_2)X_4 X_5 - \text{defuzz}(\tilde{\mu}_2)X_4 \\
 \text{defuzz}\left(\frac{d\tilde{X}_5}{dt}\right) &= \text{defuzz}(\tilde{\delta}_1)\text{defuzz}(\tilde{\beta}_1)X_3 X_5 + \text{defuzz}(\tilde{\delta}_2)\text{defuzz}(\tilde{\beta}_2)X_4 X_5 \\
 &\quad - \frac{\text{defuzz}(\tilde{r}_2)X_4 X_5}{\text{defuzz}(\tilde{\beta}_2)} - \text{defuzz}(\tilde{\mu}_2)X_5
 \end{aligned} \right\} \text{-(3)}$$

Boundedness of the System:**Theorem 1:**

The solutions of the crisp system (3) will be bounded almost.

Let $M = X_1 + X_2 + X_3 + X_4 + X_5$

Differentiate with respect to 't'

$$\frac{dM}{dt} = \frac{dX_1}{dt} + \frac{dX_2}{dt} + \frac{dX_3}{dt} + \frac{dX_4}{dt} + \frac{dX_5}{dt}$$

By our assumption, $\alpha_1 > \alpha_2$; $r_2 > r_1$; $\beta_1 > \beta_2$; $\delta_1 > \delta_2$;

$$\frac{dM}{dt} = \alpha_1 X_1 - \mu_1 X_1 - \mu_1 X_2 - \mu_2 X_3 - \mu_2 X_4 - \mu_2 X_5$$

Now choose θ such that

$$\frac{dM}{dt} \leq \alpha_1 X_1 - \theta M$$

By defining $\theta = \min(\alpha_1, \mu_1, \mu_2)$ then

$$\frac{dM}{dt} + \theta M \leq \alpha_1 X_1$$

Hence there exist a positive number L such that

$$\frac{dM}{dt} + \theta M \leq L$$

Hence the system is bounded.

Analysis of the Equilibrium:**Theorem 2**

The system is unstable if the birth rate more than the normal death rate of the susceptible non diabetic patients at the trivial point $(0, 0, 0, 0, 0)$.

Since the birth rate will be more than the death rate of a non-diabetic person,

$$\alpha_1 > \mu_1$$

The Eigen Values are

$$\lambda_1 = \alpha_1 - \mu_1, \lambda_2 = -\mu_1, \lambda_3 = -\mu_2, \lambda_4 = -\mu_2, \lambda_5 = -\mu_2$$

Here, $\lambda_2, \lambda_3, \lambda_4, \lambda_5 < 0$, but $\lambda_1 > 0$ because of $\alpha_1 > \mu_1$.

The system is unstable if the birth rate more than the normal death rate of the susceptible non diabetic patients at the trivial point $(0, 0, 0, 0, 0)$.

Theorem 3

The system is stable when there is no diabetic patient

In this case, there is no diabetic patient, so the system will depend only on non diabetic patients and their rate of infections and recovery.

Here there will be very low (more or less 0) diabetic increasing rate and infected death rate (because of our biological assumption).

Also there will not be any immune rate for diabetic case. So we will have

$$\alpha_2 < \mu_1, r_2, \delta_2 < \mu_2.$$

The Eigen values are

$$\lambda_1 = \frac{\alpha_2 X_1}{\beta_1} - \mu_1, \lambda_2 = \frac{r_2 X_5}{\beta_2} - \delta_2 \beta_2 X_5 - \mu_2$$

Since $\alpha_2 < \mu_1, r_2, \delta_2 < \mu_2, \lambda_1 < 0, \lambda_2 = 0$

The system is stable when there are no diabetic patients.

Theorem 4:

The system is stable depending on the immune system of the patient, when there is no infection.

If there is no infection, the infected rate will be very much low (more or less 0). This will mostly depend of the immune system of the both diabetic and non diabetic patients.

β_1 and β_2 will be more compared to infection rate. Now let us discuss about the stability.

The Eigen values are

$$\lambda_1 = -\mu_2, \lambda_2 = \frac{r_2(X_2)}{\beta_2} - \mu_2, \lambda_3 = \frac{r_1 X_1}{\beta_1} - \mu_2$$

$\lambda_1 < 0$ but λ_2, λ_3 depends on the values of β_1, β_2

The system is stable depending on the immune system of the patient, when there is no infection

Theorem 5:

The system is asymptotically stable in the interior equilibrium point.

By solving this we get the Eigen values as follows

$$X_1 = \frac{1}{r_1} \left(\frac{\beta_1 \mu_2 + \delta_1 \beta_1^2}{\frac{\delta_1 \alpha_1 \beta_1^2 r_2 - \delta_1 \beta_1^2 \mu_1 r_2 - \delta_1 \alpha_2 \beta_1 \beta_2 \mu_2 - r_1 r_2 \mu_2 - \delta_2 \alpha_2 \beta_2^2 \mu_2}{\alpha_2 \delta_1 \delta_2 \beta_1 \beta_2^2 - r_2 \alpha_2 \delta_1 \beta_1 - \delta_1 \alpha_2 \beta_1 r_2 + \delta_1 \alpha_2 \beta_1 \delta_2 \beta_2^2}} \right)$$

$$X_2 = \frac{1}{r_2} \left(\frac{\beta_2 \mu_2 - (r_2 + \delta_2 \beta_2^2)}{\frac{\delta_1 \alpha_1 \beta_1^2 r_2 - \delta_1 \beta_1^2 \mu_1 r_2 - \delta_1 \alpha_2 \beta_1 \beta_2 \mu_2 - r_1 r_2 \mu_2 - \delta_2 \alpha_2 \beta_2^2 \mu_2}{\alpha_2 \delta_1 \delta_2 \beta_1 \beta_2^2 - r_2 \alpha_2 \delta_1 \beta_1 - \delta_1 \alpha_2 \beta_1 r_2 + \delta_1 \alpha_2 \beta_1 \delta_2 \beta_2^2}} \right)$$

$$X_3 = \frac{1}{r_1 r_2} + (\alpha_2 r_2 - \alpha_2 \delta_2 \beta_2^2) \left(\frac{\alpha_1 \beta_1 r_2 - \beta_1 \mu_1 r_2 - \alpha_2 \beta_2 \mu_2}{\frac{\delta_1 \alpha_1 \beta_1^2 r_2 - \delta_1 \beta_1^2 \mu_1 r_2 - \delta_1 \alpha_2 \beta_1 \beta_2 \mu_2}{-r_1 r_2 \mu_2 - \delta_2 \alpha_2 \beta_2^2 \mu_2 + \delta_2 \beta_2^2 r_1 \mu_1} + r_2 \alpha_2 \mu_2 - r_1 r_2 \mu_1} \right)$$

$$X_4 = \frac{\beta_2}{r_1 r_2 (\delta_2 \beta_2^2 - r_2)} \left(\frac{\delta_1 \alpha_1 \beta_1^2 r_2 - \delta_1 \beta_1^2 \mu_1 r_2 - \delta_1 \alpha_2 \beta_1 \beta_2 \mu_2 - r_1 r_2 \mu_2}{\delta_1 \alpha_2 \beta_1 r_2 - \delta_1 \alpha_2 \beta_1 \delta_2 \beta_2^2} \right)$$

$$X_5 = \frac{\delta_1 \alpha_1 \beta_1^2 r_2 - \delta_1 \beta_1^2 \mu_1 r_2 - \delta_1 \alpha_2 \beta_1 \beta_2 \mu_2 - r_1 r_2 \mu_2 - \delta_2 \alpha_2 \beta_2^2 \mu_2}{\alpha_2 \delta_1 \delta_2 \beta_1 \beta_2^2 - r_2 \alpha_2 \delta_1 \beta_1 - \delta_1 \alpha_2 \beta_1 r_2 + \delta_1 \alpha_2 \beta_1 \delta_2 \beta_2^2}$$

Clearly according to Routh – Hurwitz criterion E_5^* is locally asymptotically stable if X_i 's are all positive

Figure2 showing the diagrammatic representation before Fuzzification

In the figure2, the uncertainty in the rate of changing parameter makes more complicated in finding the stability of the system. As the variation in the infections among the diabetic and non-diabetic patient according to their immune power shows this problem. As a diabetic patient while maintaining perfect diet he may be fit at that time and he improves his immune power in that situation. This makes the difference in finding the stability.

Figure showing the Fuzzified Diagrammatic Representation of the System

Figure3 showing the diagrammatic representation after Fuzzification

After the Fuzzification of the rate of changing parameters using trapezoidal fuzzy number system, the model has been stabilized. The difference in the model has been shown in figure3 using the Matlab software.

CONCLUSION:

In this work, we have discussed about SIR model and explained the deviations in the infections and the recovery from COVID-19 for the non-diabetic and diabetic patients. Though previously many works has been done, in this work we have explained the importance of immune system and its role in the recovery form the infection. By using Trapezoidal Fuzzy numbers, the uncertainty in the rate of change parameters are converted into fuzzy parameters and using basic BDM, the fuzzy model is converted into defuzzify crisp model. I have examined the local stability analysis mathematically and have derived the condition for four equilibrium points. Finally, from this model I have concluded that, the diabetics patients must follow recommended practices to avoid complications after the infection of COVID-19.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Funding

This research did not receive any funding.

REFERENCES:

1. Abdelfatah Kouidere, Lahcen EL Youssoufi, “*Optimal Control of Mathematical modeling of the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic with highlighting the negative impact of quarantine on diabetics people with Cost-effectiveness*” <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chaos.2021.110777>
2. Alok Aggarwal, “COVID-19 Risk Prediction for Diabetic Patients Using Fuzzy Inference System and Machine Learning Approaches” ,Journal of Healthcare Engineering Volume 2022, Article ID 4096950, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/4096950>
3. Ashish Kumar a, *, Anil Arora,et.al. “*Is diabetes mellitus associated with mortality and severity of COVID-19?*” A meta-analysis, 28 April 2020
4. Nitesh Dhiman, M.K. Sharma, “*Fuzzy Logic Inference System for Identification and Prevention of Coronavirus (COVID-19)*” International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering (IJITEE) ISSN: 2278-3075, Volume-9 Issue-6, April 2020
5. Princy.S1, Dr.S.S. Dhenakaran2, “ *Comparison of Triangular and Trapezoidal Fuzzy Membership Function*” IJRDO - Journal of Computer Science and Engineering, ISSN: 2456-1843
6. Laura Orioli a,c, Michel P. Hermansaet.al. “*COVID-19 in diabetic patients: Related risks and specifics of management*” ,2020
7. Lofti A Zadeh “*Fuzzy sets*, https://www.worldscientific.com/doi/abs/10.1142/9789814261302_0021
8. Ranchao Wu · Mengxin Chen, “*Hopf bifurcation and Turing instability in a predator–prey model with Michaelis–Menten functional response*”, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11071-017-4001-4>
9. Subhashis Das, Prasenjit Mahato, Sanat Kumar Mahato “*Disease control prey–predator model incorporating prey refuge under fuzzy uncertainty*” <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-020-00892-w>
10. Vijaya Lakshmi Gandhavadi Mohan Rao, Suresh Rasappan, Regan Murugesan and Vijaya Srinivasan, “*A Prey Predator Model with Vulnerable Infected Prey Consisting of Non-Linear Feedback*”<https://www.researchgate.net/deref/http%3A%2F%2Fdx.doi.org%2F10.12988%2Fams.2015.43184>
11. Vijaya Lakshmi Gandhavadi Mohan Rao, Roselyn Besi P“*Vaccination control measures of an epidemic model with long-term memristive effect*”, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cam.2022.114738> [12]
12. Vijaya Lakshmi Gandhavadi Mohan Rao, Roselyn Besi P, “*ABC Fractional Order Vaccination Model for Covid-19 with Self-Protective Measures*”,<https://doi.org/10.1007/s40819-022-01316-2>
13. Vijaya Lakshmi Gandhavadi Mohan Rao, Roselyn Besi P, “*A fractal fractional order vaccination model of COVID-19 pandemic using Adam’s moulton analysis*”, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rico.2022.100144>